

INGLIZ VA O`ZBEK TILLARIDA BIZNES VA TURIZM TERMINLARINI ISHLATISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biznes turizmiga oid bo`lgan bir qator terminlarning ingliz va o`zbek tillarida leksik-semantik xususiyatlari taxlil qilingan. Turizm- bugungi kunda mamlakat iqtisodiyotining muhim javhalaridan biri bo`lib kelmoqda. Turizmning yangi turlarini paydo bo`lishi bilan yangi terminlari ham vujudga kelmoqda. O`tgan asrda turli sohalarga oid terminlar o`zbek tiliga rus tili orqali Yevropa tillaridan o`zlashgan bo`lsa, bugungi kunga kelib, to`g`ridanto`g`ri chet tillaridan o`zlashmoqda.

Kalit so`zlar: Byudjet, termin, tur, turizm, soha, obyekt, biznes, leksik-semantik.

Let's focus on theory! It makes sense for a translation agency's blog to venture into the drylands of translation theory. Right? There are six main approaches within contemporary translation theory: sociolinguistic; communicative; hermeneutic; linguistic; literary; and semiotic. Are you ready?

1. THE SOCIOLINGUISTIC APPROACH

According to the sociolinguistic approach to translation, the social context defines what is and what is not translatable and what is or what is not acceptable through selection, filtering and even censorship. According to this perspective, a translator is necessarily the product of his or her society: our own sociocultural background is present in everything we translate. This approach was developed by the School of Tel Aviv and by linguists and professors such as Annie Brisset, Even Zohar, and Gideon Toury.

2. THE COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH

This theory is referred to as interpretive. Scholars Danica Seleskovitch and Marianne Lederer developed what they called the "theory of sense," based chiefly on the experience of conference interpreting. According to this perspective, meaning must be translated, not language. Language is nothing more than a vehicle for the message and can even be an obstacle to understanding. This explains why it is always better to deverbalize (instead of transcoding) when we translate.

3. THE HERMENEUTIC APPROACH

The hermeneutic approach is mainly based on George Steiner's research. Steiner believed of any human communication as a translation. His book *After Babel* shows that translation is not a science but rather an "exact art": a true translator should be capable of becoming a writer in order to capture what the author of the original text "means to say."

4. THE LINGUISTIC APPROACH

Linguists such as Vinay, Darbelnet, Austin, Vegliante, or Mounin, interested in language text, structuralism, and pragmatics, also examined the process of translating. From this perspective, any translation –whether it is a marketing translation, a medical translation a legal translation or another type of text– should be considered from the point of view of its fundamental units, that is the word, the syntagm, and the sentence.

5. THE LITERARY APPROACH

The literary approach does not consider that a translation is a linguistic endeavor but instead a literary one. Language has an "energy" revealed through words that the result of experiencing a culture. This charge is what gives it strength and ultimately, meaning: this is what the translation-writer should translate.

6. THE SEMIOTIC APPROACH

Semiotics is the study of signs and signification. A meaning is the result of a collaboration between a sign, an object, and an interpreter. Thus, from the perspective of semiotics, translation is thought of as a way of interpreting texts in which encyclopedic content varies and each sociocultural context is unique.

[Methodology of using the terms of business tourism in English and Uzbek languages](#)

Abstract: This article analyzes the lexical and semantic features of a number of terms related to business tourism in English and Uzbek. Tourism is one of the most important sectors of the economy today. With the emergence of new types of tourism, new terms are emerging. In the last century, terms related to various fields were introduced into Uzbek from Russian through European languages, but today they are directly derived from foreign languages.

Keywords: Budget, term, type, tourism, industry, object, business, lexicalsemantic.

Hozirgi kunda mamlakat iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishi borasida juda ko'plab ishlar olib borilmoqda. Jumladan, iqtisodiyot rivojining asosiy bo'g'inlaridan biri bo'lgan turizm sohasida ham jadal o'zgarishlarning guvohi bo'lyapmiz. Yurtboshimizning bugungi kunda turizm sohasiga oid chiqarayotgan qaror va

farmonlarini bu boradagi kamchiliklarni to'ldirishga va turizmni mamlakat miqyosiga olib chiqishga katta tashlangan qadamlar desak mubolag'a qilmagan bo'lamiz. Fikrimizning isboti sifatida, Prezidentimizning "O'zbekiston Respublikasining turizm sohasini jadal rivojlantirishni ta'minlash chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi farmoni, O'zbekiston Prezidentining 2017 yil 16 avgustdagi "2018-2019 yillarda turizm sohasini rivojlantirish bo'yicha 1-navbatdagi choratadbirlar to'g'risida"gi qarori turizm sohasida qilinayotgan ishlarni yangi bosqichga ko'tardi.

Turizm nafaqat bugungi mamlakat nigohida, balki temuriylar zamonida ham unga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Ya'ni Movarounnahrda ilk sayyohlarning safarlari Amir Temur va uning avlodlari zamonida faollashgan.

Turizm sohaning rivojlanishi, albatta, ichki iqtisodiy tuzilmalarning takomillashishiga, bundan tashqari shu soha bilan bog'liq ravishda faoliyat olib boruvchi sohalarning rivojlanishiga ham ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ammo sayohat qilish, doimiy yashash joyidan boshqa joyda dam olish, yangi hududlarni ko'rish yoki shifobaxsh hududlarda salomatligini tiklash uchun katta moliyaviy mablag'lar talab etilishi ham sir emas. Bu mablag'lar kerakli manzilga yetib borish, tunab qolish va joylashish, ovqatlanish va shu kabi turli xizmatlardan foydalanganligi uchun sarflanadi. Ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj aholi qatlamlari qisman davlatning ijtimoiy himoya siyosatidan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ushbu aholi guruhlariga maxsus sayohatlar uyushtirish tizimlari joriy etilgan va ular orqali turizm xizmatlari aynan aholining kam ta'minlangan qatlamlariga xizmat qilishi ta'minlangan.

Turizm turistik tashkilotlar tomonidan qonuniy tarzda amalga oshiriladi. Shunga ko'ra turizm bir necha xil turlarga ajratiladi: ichki turizm, xalqaro turizm, havaskorlik turizmi, biznes turizm, ekoturizm, sport turizmi, avtoturizm, bilim saviyasini kengaytirish uchun olib boriladigan turizm va boshqalar.

Biznes-tur turistning kasbiy faoliyati bilan bog'liq bo'lib, daromad keltiradigan, foyda olish maqsadlari ko'zlangan va qonunga xilof bo'lmagan har qanday tashkiliy, xo'jalik; tijorat, ishbilarmonlik faoliyati bilan bog'liq safar turi.

Kiruvchi turizm - muayyan davlat hududiga chet ellik sayyohlarning tashrifi bilan amalga oshadigan turizm. Biror davlatga keluvchi turistlar o'sha hudud uchun kiruvchi turizm subyekti hisoblanadi.

Ichki turizm- biror davlat hududida doimiy yashovchi aholi tomonidan shu davlat hududining boshqa tarafiga uyushtiriladigan turizm. Ichki turizm termini so'nggi yillarda keng iste'molda qo'llanuvchi leksik birlikka aylanib bormoqda.

Ijtimoiy turizm-sayohat xarajatlari davlat budjeti, budjetdan tashqari fondlar, ish beruvchi hisobidan to'liq yoki qisman qoplanadigan turizm.

Guruhiy (paket) tur - bir necha turistik xizmatlarning jamlanmasidan iborat tur. Bu jamlanma o'z ichiga qayta ishlanadigan turoperator, aviauchish, xizmat ko'rsatish, transfer, yashash joyi bilan ta'minlash kabi xizmatlarni oladi.

Xizmat turizmi-turistning kasbiy va savdo-sotiqqa oid qiziqishi bilan bog'liq turizm turi. Shaxsiy xizmat safari va turli tadbirlarni o'tkazish kabilarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Individual turizm-bir yoki bir necha turistlarning ixtiyori bo'yicha ularning buyurtmasiga asoslangan joylashtirish, ovqatlantirish, transfer, ekskursiya va ko'ngilochar dasturlarni o'z ichiga oluvchi xizmatlar to'plamidan iborat turizm.

Rekreatsion turizmi. Tashkil etilish maqsadi jihatdan xizmat turizmiga qaramaqarshi tarzda hordiq chiqarish uchun uyushtiriladigan sayohat.

Ekoturizm ekoturistik obyektlarga (estetik zavq beradigan tabiatning betakror joylari, shifobaxsh tabiiy maskanlar, tabiiy va antropogen geotuzilmalar, jism va tabiat hodisalari, tarixiy-madaniy meros obyektlari, mahalliy xalqning etnik yashash tarzi kabilarga) sog'lomlashtirish, davolanish, dam olish, ularni o'rganish, jismoniy rivojlanishni ta'minlashga qaratilgan, tashkiliy tarzda uyushtirilgan ommaviy turizm.

Turizmning yangi turlarini paydo bo'lishi bilan bog'liq tarzda yangi terminlar ham vujudga kelmoqda. Shu terminlar orasidan biznes turizmiga to'xtalib o'tsak. Hozirgi o'zbek tilining ko'p ishlatiladigan izohli lug'atida biznes (inl.business-ish, mashg'ulot) daromad keltiradigan, foyda olish maqsadlari ko'zlangan har qanday tashkiliy, xo'jalik faoliyati; tijorat; ishbilarmonlik degan ma'nolari keltirilgan. Turizm (fr. tourisme < tour-aylanish, sayr (sayohat) qilish.

1. Ham dunyoni ko'rish, bilim olish, o'rganish, ham dam olish maqsadida tashkil etiladigan sayr sayohat. Turizmni tobora rivojlanayotganini e'tiborga olib, turistik poyezdlar marshruti yanada ko'paytirildi. "Fan va turmush"

2. Sport. Organizmni jismoniy chiniqtirish maqsadida uyushtiriladigan jamoaviy yurishlar, safarlar.

Oxford dictionary of English kitobini kuzatganimizda business so'ziga o'zbek tiliga nisbatan kengroq ta'rif berilganligini guvohi bo'ldik:

1. The activity of making, buying, selling or supplying goods or services for money. (Pul topish maqsadida mahsulot tayyorlash sotish, sotib olish, ta'minlash yoki xizmat ko'rsatish);

2. Work that is part of your job. (Kasbingizning bir qismi bo'lgan ish);

3. The amount of work done by a company, etc; the rate or quality of this work. (Kompaniya tomonidan qilingan ishlar miqdori; shu ishning sifati yoki darajasi);

4. Something that concerns a particular person or organization. (Biror kompaniyaga yoki shaxsga aloqador narsa);

5. Things that need to be discussed or done (Qilinishi yoki maslahatlashishi kerak bo'lgan masala);

6. A situation or activity, especially one that you have a particular opinion about or attitude towards. (O'z munosabatingiz bo'lgan vaziyat).

Yuqorida turizmni bir necha guruhlariga bo'lganimiz kabi biznes turizm ham o'z ichida bir necha turlarga bo'linib ketadi: individual sayohatlar, guruhli sayohatlar, tadbirlar (uchrashuvlar, rag'batlantirishlar, anjumanlar, ko'rgazmalar (MICE), jamoani shakllantirish va o'quv safarlaridagi joylarni almashtirish.

Biznes turizmi ko'plab biznes korporatsiyalar bilan ishlaydi: mehmonxonalar tarmog'i, ko'pgina mamlakatlarda professional ravishda birlashtirilgan savdo yarmarkalari va ko'rgazmalarining, biznes markazlarining tashkilotchilari. Albatta, har bir sohasining alohida terminlari mavjud. Biz bu maqolada biznes turizmiga oid bo'lgan bir qator terminlarning ingliz va o'zbek tillarida leksiksemantik xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Barchamizga ma'lumki, O'zbekistonda turizm jadallik bilan rivojlanib borayotgan, mamlakat iqtisodiyotiga salmoqli hissasini qo'shadigan sohalardan biri hisoblanadi. Har bir sohaning o'ziga xos terminologiyasi mavjud. Shuningdek, turizm terminologiyasi ham o'zbek terminologik sistemasida katta o'rinni egallaydi. Uning boyib borishida lisoniy (lingvistik) va nolisoniy (ekstralingvistik) omillar ajratiladi. O'tgan asrda turli sohalarga oid terminlar o'zbek tiliga rus tili orqali Yevropa tillaridan o'zlashgan bo'lsa, bugungi kunga kelib, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri chet tillaridan o'zlashmoqda va misol tariqasida, biznes turizmiga oid bo'lgan so'zlarning o'zbek tilidagi leksiksemantik manolarini quyidagi jadvalda ko'rib chiqamiz:

Shartnoma	Tomonlar (ikki yoki bir nechta shaxs) o'rtasida tuzilgan, ularning huquq va majburiyatlari qayd etilgan bitim.
Bilet	Biror narsa (transport vositalari)dan foydalanish, biror joyga (teatr, sport saroyi va b.) kirish huquqini beradigan hujjat, chipta.
Reys	Kema, samolyot, mashina kabi transport vositalarining ma'lum mashrut bo'yicha qatnov yo'li.
Viza	Biror xorijiy davlatga borish, unda yashash va uning hududidan o'tish uchun tegishli ma'muriy idora tomonidan pasportga qo'yiladigan maxsus ruxsat. belgisi.

Tur	Turistlarni aniq yo`nalish bo`yicha xizmatlar majmuasi va muddati aniq bo`lgan tashishni uyushtirish.
Turizm industriyasi	Turizmning material-texnik bazasini tashkil etuvchi xalq xo`jaligining turli sohalari yig`indisi.
Flotel	Suzib yuruvchi mehminxona kemasi. Suvdagi ulkan otel, maxsus jihoxlangan bo`ladi. Qulay nomerlardan tashqari, yaxshi dam olish uchun qulaylik yaratilgan, vaqtinchalik ofisdan foydalanish, operativ vosita aloqalari: telefon, kseroks, faks va boshqa xizmatlar ko`rsatiladi
Turistik uy	Faol harakatdagi turistlarni qisqa muddatga dam olish uchun mo`ljallangan boshpana. Bular asosan tog` yonbag`irlarida jiylashgan bo`lib, sharoiti minimal darajada bo`ladi
Rotel	Harakatlanuvchi mehmonxona, vagon ko`rinishidagi bir yoki ikki o`rinli nomerga ega bo`lgan, kiyinish xonasi, umumiy ovqatlanish, umumiy xojatxonaga ega bo`lgan mehmonxona

Patsionat	Erkin shaklda, qurilish paytida mehmonxona sifatida barpo etilmagan uylardir. Parsionatlar 10-20 kishiga mo`lallangan.
Motel	Avtoturistlar uchun mehmonxona. Qulay nomerlardan tashari turistlarga avtomashinalari turar joylari bilan ham ta`minlanadi. Odatda motellarda restoran, bar, kino-video filmlarko`rish, konferensiya zallari, kino zallari, basseynlar, tennis kortlari ham xizmat ko`rsatadi
Voucher	Ko`rsatiladigan asosiy xizmatlarning (mehmomxonada to`xtash, ovqatlanish, transport va b.) haqqi to`langanligi haqida tasdiqlangan hujjat.
Diller	Turistik firmalarmi oldi sotisi bilan shug`ullanuvchi turistik firmalar, ko`pincha ular o`z hisobiga va o`zining nomiga ish olib boradi.
Motel	Unchalik katta bo`lmagan suvdagi mehmonxona. Jihozlangan qulayliklarga ega bo`lgan kema.
Brontlash	Muayyan turist uchun mehmonxona xonalaridan birining, transport vositasining, madaniy tomosha uchun biletni oldindan bandlash

Tabldot	Restoranlarda taomga nisbatan qo'llanuvchi, gazakdan tortib desert miqdorigacha chegaralangan va ovqatlarga umumiy narxlar o'rnatilgan xizmat ko'rsatish turi. Odatda esa har bir taomga alohida belgilangan narxlar asosida xizmat ko'rsatiladi.
Gid	Turistlarga shaharning yoki ma'lum diqqatga sazovor joylarini ko'rsatuvchi, bir yoki bir nechta tillarni biluvchi professional yo'l boshlovchi. Bu termin iste'molda faol qo'llanadi.
Tranzit	Bir hududdan ikkinchi hududga uchinchi hudud orqali 24 soatdan ko'p bo'lmagan vaqtda yo'lovchi, yuk kabilarni olib o'tish. Bu termin tranzit yuk, tranzit yo'lovchi kabi birikma shaklidagi boshqa terminlarni hosil qilishda ham qatnashadi.
Transfer	Turistik markazning ichkarisida turistni istalgan joyga tashish (vokzal, aeroport, dengiz portidan mehmonxonaga yoki shu yo'nalishning qaramaqarshisi; bir vokzal, aeroport, dengiz portidan boshqasiga; mehmonxonadan teatrga yoki qarama-qarshi yo'nalishda tashish).
Lyuks	Mehmonxonadagi nomerlar kategoriyasi bo'lib, mijozga taqdim etilayotgan xonalar hashami. Bu termin tarjima lug'atlarda "hasham, dabdaba" kabi ma'nolarni ifodalashi qayd etiladi, biroq turizm sohasida ingliz tilidagi shakli kabi qo'llanadi.
Turbroker	O'zining shaxsiy transportiga ega bo'lmagan, ammo turpaket ichiga kirgan barcha turlarni va taqdim qilingan xizmatlar uchun ularni ijaraga berib turuvchi shaxs yoki kompaniya
Turpaket	Turizm jarayonida turistning ehtiyojini qondirish uchun kamida ikkita turistik xizmatlar (ishlar, tovarlar) dan tashkil topgan xizmatlar majmuasi.
Botel	Suzib yuruvchi mehmonxona. Mehmonxonaning bu ko'rinishdagi turi O'zbekiston turizmida uchramaydi.
Aerofobiya	Uchish vaqtida tashvishli holatga o'zgarish, uchish qo'rquvi.
Yashil yo'lak	Bojxona deklaratsiyasi talab qilinmaydigan yuklarni o'tkazish chegarasi. Bu ham metafora asosida hosil qilingan terminlar sirasiga kiradi. Yuklarni muayyan ruxsatnomasiz

	o`tkazish mumkinligini bildiradi.
Biznes klass	samolyotda qulayligi jihatdan birinchi va ekonomklass.
Konsullik bo`limi	Elchixonadagi bo`linma. Boshqa davlat hududida elchilik vazifalarini amalga oshiradi. Mahalliy hokimiyat organlari bilan aloqalarni o`rnatadi, fuqarolariga xizmat ko`rsatish bilan shug`ullanadi, hujjatlar (viza, passport, notarial hujjatlar, ma`lumotnoma)ni rasmiylashtirish va qonun doirasidagi masalalarni hal qiladi.
Oferta	Ko`rsatiladigan xizmat bo`yicha bitimning yakunlanganligini bildiruvchi rasmiy taqdimnoma.
Ryokan	Yaponiyada Edo davridagi tarixiy an`ana va estetik asosda qurilgan mehmonxonalar.
Turistik klass	Mansionga yaqin bo`lgan, qulaylik darajasi uncha yuqori bo`lmagan ekonom klassdagi mehmonxona.
Bungalo	Mehmonxonalarda quriluvchi bir qavatdan iborat, ayvoni bo`lgan uy.
Yuk me`yori	aviakompaniya tomonidan qabul qilingan bepul yuk tashish uchun zarur bo`lganmaksimal vazn yoki yuklarning miqdori.
A la carte	har bir ovqatga alohida narx belgilangan menyu yoki restoran
Yengil nonushta.	kofe (yoki choy, sharbat), bulochka, saryog` va murabbodan iborat nonushta.
Outlet	eng so`nggi modadagi kiyimlarni ijaraga berishga ixtisoslashgan savdo markazi.
Animatsiya	dam oluvchilarning bo`sh vaqtini mazmunli o`tkazishga xizmat qiluvchi dasturlar majmui.
Shvedcha stol	kafe va restoranlarda o`z-o`ziga xizmat ko`rsatish shakli. Tashrif buyuruvchilar yagona belgilangan narxlarda zalga qo`yilgan ovqatlardan istalgan miqdorda va xohishiga ko`ra tanavvul qilishlari mumkin.
Vegitariancha stol	tirik jonivorlar qismlaridan tayyorlangan ovqatlar butunlay tortilmaydigan ovqatlanish turi.
Amerikancha nonushta	yengil nonushta, kolbasa, pishloq, issiq ovqatlar (omlet, sosiska)dan iborat nonushta
Halol stol	islom shariati tanovvul qilishga ijozat bergan yegulik va

	ichimliklardan iborat ovqatlanish turi.
Inglizcha nonushta	mevali sharbat, qovurilgan tuxum, tost, saryog`, murabbo, choy yoki kofedan iborat nonushta.

Bundan tashqari, biz turistik sayohatga otlanganimizda biznes turizmiga oid yana bir qancha terminlarga duch kelamiz. Bunga misol qilib quyidagilarni keltirishimiz mumkin: Bir yulduzli mehmonxona - byudjet hisobidagi, shaharlarning markazida joylashtirilgan, minimum qulayliklarga ega bo`lgan mehmonxona.

Ikki yulduzli mehmonxona - bir yulduzligiga qo`shimcha bari va restorani bo`lgan turistik klasli mehmonxona.

Uch yulduzli mehmonxona - o`rtacha darajadagi, lekin xizmat ko`rsatish darajasi yuqori bo`lgan mehmonxona.

To`rt yulduzli mehmonxona - birinchi klasli, juda yuqori sifatli yashash va a`lo darajadagi xizmat ko`rsatish imkoniyatiga ega mehmonxona.

Besh yulduzli mehmonxona - yuqori kategoriyali, xizmat ko`rsatish va yashash o`ta yuqori darajadagi mehmonxona.

Yulduzlar sistemasi - Fransiya, Avstriya, Vengriya, Arabiston, Rossiya, O`zbekiston va boshqa davlatlarning mehmonxonolari tasnifida keng qo`llaniladigan tizimlash shakli. Buyuk Britaniya turagentlik assotsiatsiyasi - British Travel Authority (BTA) yulduzlar sistemasi bo`yicha mehmonxonalarini quyidagi turlarga ajratadi.

Har bir turizm turining o`ziga xos terminlari bor. Shuningdek, biznes turizmining ham. Bularga biz sayohat uchun yo`lga otlanganimizdan boshlab duch kelamiz. Undan keyingi jarayonlar ham o`z terminlariga ega. Biznes turizmiga oid bo`lgan so`zlarning Oxford dictionary of English, Longmen dictionarylarida quyidagi manolarini kuzatdik:

1. Plane- n. vehicle that flies in the air and has wings and at list one engine.
2. Airline-n a company that provides regular flights to take passengers and goods to different places.
3. Arrivals-n an act of coming or being brought to a place. * A person or a thing that comes to a plase.

* The time when a new technology or idea is introduced

4. Departure-n the act of leaving a place.

* A plane, train, etc. leaving a place at a particular time.

* An action that is different from what is usual or expected

5. Departure lounge-n a place people wait for being ready.

6. Check-in-n the place where you go first when you arrive at an airport, to show your ticket, etc.
 - * The act of showing your ticket, etc. when you arrive at an airport.
7. Flight-n travel by plane.
8. Security-n the act involved in protecting a country, building or person against attack, danger, etc.
 - * Protection against something bad that might happen in future.
 - * The state of feeling happy and safe from danger or worry.
 - * Documents proving that somebody is the owner of shares, etc in a particular company.
9. Baggage reclaim-n a place at an airport where you get your suitcases, etc. Again after you have flown.
10. Window seat-n a seat next to the window
11. Aisle seat-n a seat next to the passage.
12. Boarding pass-n a card that you have to show before get on the plane.
13. First class-n the best and expensive seats.
14. Business class-n expensive seats but not expensive than first class.
15. Economy class-n the cheapest seats in a plane.
16. Booking-n an arrangement that you make in advance to buy a ticket to travel somewhere, go to the theatre.
 - * An arrangement for somebody to perform at a theatre, in a cinema, etc.
17. Room service-n a service provided in a hotel, by which guests can order food and drink to be brought to their rooms.
18. Hotel-n a building where people pay to stay and eat meals.
19. Motel-n a hotel for people travelling by car, usually with a plane for the car near each room.
20. Inn-n a small hotel, especially an old one in the countryside. Also used in the names of some big modern hotels.
21. Guesthouse-n a private house where people can pay to stay and have meals.
22. Hostel/youth hostel-n a very cheap hotel where people can stay for a short time while they are travelling.
23. Above the line- commission received from advertising like TV, radio, poster, and press
24. Advance order-order placed prior to movie-in date for an exhibition
25. Advance rate- discount rates to entice guests to book in advance
26. Allotment- the number of hotel rooms available for sale by a agent or supplier .

27. Attrition- a clause include in a hotel contract to ensure an organization fulfils their contracted obligations
28. ALOS- acronym for average length of stay.
29. Best available Rate [BAR] - a pricing system used by hotels to define a rate based on the demand and occupancy a room
30. BKG-acronym for booking.
31. Boardroom setup- room set that seats executive along a long table with the chief executive at a hotel
32. Breakout room- smaller ancillary room to ballroom that can be used by smaller groups for one reason or another
33. Butler service- guests are served hors d'oeuver on platters by servers
34. CRS- acronym for central reservation system.
35. C&I- conference and Incentive booking.
36. Cut-off date- date at which all unused guest rooms in a room block be released to public
37. Distressed Inventory- last-minute discounted hotel rooms to ensure a property reaches full capacity
38. Early arrival- an agreement with a hotel that allows confirmed guests to checkin before the standart time
39. Half- board- a rete that includes a bed, breakfast, and a choice of lunch or dinner
40. Heads in bed- the hospitality industry's reason for existence, to sell hotel rooms and increase the occupancy rate of the hotel
41. KPI [Key Performance Indicator] - metric widely used as a measurement of business performance
42. Market share- a percentage of business within a market category.
43. Merchant rate-a business model used by OTAs to makeup hotel net rates to sell to the public
44. OTA- acronym for online trevel agent
45. Overbooking- when more rooms are sold than are physically available to sell
46. Room block- a specific set or count rooms that are reserved for guests in a group
47. Room class- a grouping of rooms based on similar value characteristic.
48. Room nights- rooms blocked or occupied multiplied by the number of nights the room are reserved
49. Room rack- a contually updated card index system reflecting occupied and vacant rooms

50. Run of house [ROH] - ROH in hotel terms means a basic room type with no guaranteed specific amenities .
51. Transient business- segment of business comprised of individual booking as opposed to bookings from a group .
52. Preferred rate- a negotiated rate between the hotel and specific client .
53. Qualified rate- a rate that is only offered based on qualifications such as a corporate or proportional package
54. Quin- refers to hotel rooms that can accommodate five people
55. Rack rate- the original price of hotel room before any discounts or proportional rates are applied.
56. Receptive operators- specialists who handle arrangements for incoming visitors, such as airport transfers, restaurants, and accommodations .
57. Repeat booking- when repeat business is booked on behalf of the same client.

Yuqoridagi natijalardan ko`rinib turibdiki, O`zbek tilida turizm terminologiyasi ilk shakllanish bosqichida bo`lib, soha rivoji natijasida uning tarkibi yangi maxsus birliklar bilan boyib bormoqda. Turizm iqtisodiy faoliyat natijasida dastlab Angliyada vujudga kelganligi uchun uning vatani sifatida shu hudud e`tirof etiladi. Shuningdek, xalqaro turizm terminologiyasida ingliz tilining yetakchi mavqeda ekanligini inobatga olsak, o`zbek tilidagi o`zlashmalarning asosiy qismi shu tildan o`zlashganligi tabiiy holdir, albatta.

Ikki til ya`ni o`zbek va ingliz tillarini bir soha-turizm terminologiyalari bo`yicha qiyoslaganimizda, o`zbek tilida ayrim terminlarning o`z holicha, ayrimlarining muqobil varianti qo`llanganligining guvohi bo`ldik. Ingliz tilida ko`plab terminlar inglizchada berilgan. Ammo bu tilda ham boshqa tillardan olingan so`zalarni uchratishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa o`rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, o`zbek tilidagi mavjud turizm terminlarining izohli, elektron va tarjima lug`atlarini yaratish o`zbek terminologiyasining muhim vazifalardan biridir. Izohli lug`atlarda, turistik terminlar uchun tuziladigan maxsus lug`atlarda terminlarning berilishi va izohlanishi o`quvchining shu fan borasidagi eng zaruriy va umumiy tushunchalar bilan tanishishiga va uning bilim saviyasini oshirishga, bundan tashqari shu sohaga qiziqish paydo qilishga ham xizmat qiladi.